

Studies in Thiazolidones. Part IV. Synthesis of 2-Imino-4-oxo-5-thiazolidine-acetic Acids

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The reaction of thiourea with diversely substituted N atom has been studied with a view to ascertaining its orientation in the thiazolidine ring having benzyl, phenyl, and naphthyl groups as substituents at C₂ and N₃ in the ring. Probable physiological properties of the compounds have also been tested.

Tambach¹ and Andreasch² reported the reaction between thiourea and maleic or fumaric acid to yield 2-imino-4-oxo-5-thiazolidine-acetic acids. Their structure was proved by ring-degradation method. Martin³ condensed *N*-substituted maleimides with thioureas and obtained similar products, also proved by the degradation method. Recently Nagasaka and Nukina⁴ have also confirmed the structure, using spectral evidence. Arakelian⁵ has condensed symmetrical dibutylthiourea with maleic anhydride and prepared 2-butylimino-3-*n*-butyl-4-oxo-5-thiazolidine-acetic acid.

The present work has been undertaken with a two-fold purpose, primarily to investigate this reaction of thiourea with different substituents of nitrogen atom and to examine its orientation in the thiazolidine ring, where benzyl, phenyl, and naphthyl groups are substituents at C₂ and N₃ of the thiazolidine ring and secondarily to test these compounds for their probable physiological activity since unsubstituted maleic acid and its thiol adducts show antimitotic activity on culture of chick fibroblasts⁶.

Diversely substituted thioureas were prepared according to Trivedi *et al.*⁷ and these were condensed with maleic anhydride in methylethyl ketone or ethanol by heating for 10 to 18 hr. The following types of 2-imino-4-oxothiazolidine-acetic acids have been synthesised:

1. *Annalen*, 1894, 280, 239.
2. *Monatsh.*, 1895, 18, 789.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1515.
4. *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1954, 57, 169.
5. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 465.
6. *Marrion et al., Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, 3, 335.
7. *This Journal*, 1956, 33, 423, 657.

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TABLE II (contd.)

R.	R'	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur. Found.	% Sulphur. Reqd.
B: Phenyl-benzyl series.					
2-Me. C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	230°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.02	9.04
4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	140°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.75	0.91
4-OPr. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	144°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.22	7.40
4-C ₂ H ₅ O. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	141°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.16	0.34
4-C ₂ H ₅ O. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	158°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.31	0.16
4-C ₂ H ₅ O. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-OBu. C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	148°	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.00	0.25
Ph.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	208°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.20	0.41
4-OMe. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	140°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.94	7.13
4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	210°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.30	7.48
4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	143°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.42	7.65
4-OPr. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	145°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.58	0.71
4-OBu. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	180°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.35	0.62
4-OBu. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	210°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	6.80	7.02
4-C ₂ H ₅ O. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	136°	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	0.78	0.95
4-C ₂ H ₅ O. C ₆ H ₄ -	4-OEt. C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	125°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.43	0.61
C: Benzyl-naphthyl series.					
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	180°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.00	8.20
2-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	135°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.64	0.82
3-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	212°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.36	7.54
3-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	142°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.60	0.82
3-IC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	145°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ IS	6.08	6.20
4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	151°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.32	7.54
4-IC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	169°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ IS	6.00	6.20
2-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	163°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.34	7.54
2-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	175°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	6.65	6.82
3-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	155°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.37	7.54
3-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	215°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.64	0.82
3-IC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	144°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ IS	6.00	6.20
4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	245°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	7.35	7.54
4-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	245°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	0.65	0.82
4-IC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	141°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ IS	0.35	0.20
D: Phenyl-phenyl series.					
Ph.	Ph.	250°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.70	0.82
"	2-Tol.	207°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.25	0.41
"	2-OMe. C ₆ H ₄ -	210°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.18	0.30
"	3-NO ₂ . C ₆ H ₄ -	147°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.42	8.62
"	4-Tol.	213°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.28	0.41
"	4-OMe. C ₆ H ₄ -	215°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.19	0.30
"	4-NO ₂ . C ₆ H ₄ -	122°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.41	8.62
2-Tol.	Ph.	206°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.23	0.41
"	2-Tol.	220°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.18	0.30
"	2-OMe. C ₆ H ₄ -	140°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.43	8.66
"	3-NO ₂ . C ₆ H ₄ -	127°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.15	8.31
"	4-Tol.	245°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.20	0.30
"	4-NO ₂ . C ₆ H ₄ -	200°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.16	8.31
4-Tol.	Ph.	210°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	0.55	0.41
"	2-Tol.	250°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.82	9.00
4-OMe. C ₆ H ₄ -	2-Tol.	213°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.48	8.65
4-Tol.	3-NO ₂ . C ₆ H ₄ -	122°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.20	8.31

TABLE II (contd.)

R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Tol-	4-Tol-	251°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.76	9.00
"	4-OMe.C ₆ H ₄ -	150°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.43	8.65
4-OMe.C ₆ H ₄ -	4-Tol-	244°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.81	8.68
"	4-OMe.C ₆ H ₄ -	215°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ S	8.05	8.29
4-Tol-	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -	206°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ S	8.10	8.31
E: Phenyl-naphthyl series.					
Ph-	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	212°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.42	8.51
2-Tol-	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	138°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.00	8.20
4-Tol-	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	136°	"	8.32	8.20
4-OMe.C ₆ H ₄ -	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	143°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	7.64	7.88
Ph-	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	105°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.33	8.51
2-Tol-	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	127°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.02	8.20
4-Tol-	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	140°	"	8.31	8.20
4-OMe.C ₆ H ₄ -	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	146°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.12	7.88

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